

Speculation on Gibbs' Paradox Part 5

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It is known that the entropy of an ideal gas is extensive in the $N \rightarrow$ infinite limit (thermodynamic limit), i.e. in the case that Stirling's approximation to first order: $\ln(N!) = N \ln(N)$ holds. Stirling's approximation to third order is: $\ln(N!) = N \ln(N) - N + \sqrt{2\pi N}$ and the third order term breaks extensivity. For particles of the order of 6×10^{23} (Avogadro's number), a first order approximation is sufficient. We suggest that if one considers an ideal gas with V, N, T with no fluctuations in the number of particles in each spatial density region and with particles taken to be identical, then one obtains the first order Stirling's approximation $n! = n^n$ if one wishes the number of macrostates to match those of any equal placed set of partitions' macrostates.. Thus, this is the picture associated with entropy extensivity, one of no fluctuations of particle density in space as seems to be known in the literature (1), (2). The crude approximation $n! = n^n$ is equivalent to this physical picture (as is known in the literature (1), (2)). The point we make is that (1) and (2) are rather recent contributions (2011, 2023).

Average Picture

On average, one expects the spatial density of an ideal gas to be constant. This of course bypasses the notion of macrostates for which there are different numbers of particles in different regions of space, i.e. a V, N, T case with all N particles at the right or left of the container. In general, if entropy is $-k \ln(\text{number of states})$ this spatial particle number fluctuations must be considered. These macrostates average out to a constant density in space. If, however, one were to consider only the case of identical particles in an ideal gas with no spatial density fluctuations, then one would have the following condition:

$$V^N / N! = \{ (V/a)^{N/a} / (N/a)! \}^a \quad ((1))$$

Here a is an integer.

((1)) leads to:

$$N! = (N/a)!^a / (1/a)^N \quad ((2))$$

One seeks an approximation for $N!$ such that a disappears from ((2)). The simplest solution is:

$$\text{If } N! = N^N, \text{ then one has } N^N \text{ versus } (N/a)^N / (1/a)^N \quad ((3))$$

The simplest solution is:

$$N! = N^N \quad ((4))$$

This is a very simplistic approximation which, if it holds, would have to hold for a very large N .

The point is that we try to obtain a mathematical approximation based on a physical example and the assumption that the entropy of identical particles with no spatial particle number fluctuations (i.e. constant density everywhere) is the same as adding the entropy for any number of partitions of V . Here we consider entropy as being the \ln of the number of macrostates, but don't impose the \ln , as it is not needed for finding the math approximation that yields the required result.

Out of curiosity, one may see that: $n! = n \text{ power } n \exp(-n)$ is also a solution of ((2)) i.e.

$$\text{LHS } N! = N \text{ power } N \exp(-N) \quad \text{RHS } (N/a) \text{ power } N \exp(-N) / (1/a) \text{ power } N \quad ((5))$$

Discussion

It is certainly possible to consider permutations of particles in a gas of V, N, T such that the spatial density is constant everywhere. This means no spatial particle number fluctuations. The expression:

$$V \text{ power } N / N! \quad ((6))$$

However, contains all possible spatial fluctuations and so a priori, it seems that one would need a different expression than ((6)). The idea we use above is to consider an approximation to $N!$ which would allow the expression ((6)) to essentially remove its spatial fluctuations. We find that in fact two solutions achieve this goal. The expression $N! = N \text{ power } N$ is an approximation, but the RHS is guaranteed to be larger than the LHS. The idea seems to be that as $N \rightarrow \infty$, $N \text{ power } N$ dominates any successive terms which are of a lower order, e.g. $N \text{ power } N-1$ or lower. As a result, there is mathematical merit in the approximation $N! = N \text{ power } N$ as long as N is extremely large as it would be in the case of an Avogadro's number of particles 6×10^{23} .

We suggest that this kind of reasoning bypasses the steepest descent approaches required to prove Stirling's approximation. Physically, we suggest that it is important to realize that spatial particle number fluctuations are real and are part of a counting of macrostates, so the approximation $N! = N \text{ power } N$, which leads to entropy extensivity for $N \rightarrow \infty$ does so by removing these physical fluctuations. As a result, it is only in an extreme limit that one obtains extensivity. In terms of physical macrostates, the entropy of a sub-partitions of an ideal gas is less than that of the full V gas at the same T . It is just that the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit dominates other large terms which are still smaller than the first dominant $N \text{ power } N$ term. This we argue can be a source of confusion when considering extensivity of thermodynamic entropy and the idea of macrostates (for which non-constant density must be considered).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider an ideal gas with N, V, T and place in it equally spaced partitions. If the spatial density remains constant and one has identical particles, the number of macrostates (product of the macrostates in each partition) remains the same. The equation $V \text{ power } N / N!$,

however, accounts for identical particles, but considers all possible densities. We ask if there is some approximation for $N!$ which only includes the constant density scenario, i.e.

$$V \text{ power } N / N! = \{ (V/a) \text{ power } (N/a) / (N/a) ! \} \text{ power } a$$

We find two solutions: $N! = N \text{ power } N$ (which is very drastic and only holds for $N \rightarrow \infty$) and $N! = N \text{ power } N - N$. Mathematically, $N \text{ power } N = N!$ is reasonable, but only if N is extremely large as it would be for $N = 6 \times 10^{23}$ particles. Thus, mathematically the approximation holds in such a case, but physically it removes all spatial density fluctuations as is known in the literature (1), (2).

In other words, the drastic approximation $n! = n \text{ power } n$ is physically equivalent to considering the number of macrostates in V, N, T as being the same as the product of macrostates for each partition. This set of macrostates, however, is not full entropy (even when the \ln is taken) as entropy considers spatial fluctuations.

References

1. https://didier.lairez.fr/pperso/theory/post_stirling/
2. Verseeagh, M. and Dieks, D. The Gibbs paradox and the distinguishability of identical particles (2011) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1012.4111>